

Introductory Programming Course Survey – 2021 version

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A Global Survey of Introductory Programming Courses. In Proceedings of the 55th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 1 (SIGCSE 2024). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626252.3630761>

Survey:

Q1a: What is your country?

Q1b: What is your university?

Q2a: Course code?

Q2b: Course name?

Q2c: Faculty, School or Department (immediate organisational unit) offering this course?

Q3: At your University, approximately how many students are undertaking this course in 2021 (across all cohorts, locations, and modes)?

Q4: For the remainder of the questions, unless otherwise indicated, please answer with information as it currently stands, even if this information has changed since the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Which programming language(s) is/are being used in the first programming course that students encounter in their studies? (More than one may be chosen if appropriate)

Actionscript, Ada, Alice, C, C++, C#, Delphi/Object Pascal, Eiffel, Fortran, Haskell, Java, Javascript, jBase, Lisp, Matlab, Objective-C, Perl, PHP, Processing, Python, Ruby, Visual Basic/VB.NET, Other language

Q4x What other language/s do you use for the first programming course?

[The following block repeats for each language that is chosen]

Q4a which of the following is true? <Language> is used

- a) For the whole of the first programming course
- b) For the first part of the programming course, followed by another language or languages
- c) After another language in the programming course

Q4b This question asks about why <language> was chosen for your course, and asks you to rate the importance of each reason. If a reason is not applicable, please choose N/A. Otherwise, how important was each reason?

Choices are: N/A, not at all important, slightly important, moderately important, very important, extremely important.

Reasons are:

Availability/cost to students; departmental politics, ease of installation, easy to find appropriate texts, extensions/libraries available, interpreted language, marketable to students, object-oriented language, online community/help available, OS/Machine

limitations of department, pedagogical benefits, perceived suitability for online delivery, platform independence, relevant to industry, structure of degree.

Q4c How difficult do you think <language> is for students to learn?

Extremely easy, somewhat easy, neither easy nor difficult, somewhat difficult, extremely difficult

Q4d How useful do you think <language> is for teaching the fundamental concepts of programming?

Extremely useful, very useful, moderately useful, slightly useful, not at all useful.

[End of repeating block]

Q5 This question asks you about the possible factors that may influence you to change language in your course (even if there are no current plans to do so). Please enter numbers to place in rank order the following factors for changing the language in your course (where 1 is the most important). Rank a minimum of three responses.

Availability/Cost to students, Comparison with other courses, Departmental politics, Ease of installation, easy to find appropriate texts, extensions/libraries available, GUI interface available, Interpreted language, marketable to students, more suitable for online delivery, object-oriented language, online community and help available, OS/Machine limitations of dept, pedagogical benefits, platform independence, relevance to industry, structure of degree, student/parent pressure, other reason.

Q5x What other reason might influence you to change language?

Q6 What paradigm is being taught - regardless of what is traditionally thought to apply to the language being taught?

procedural, object-oriented, functional, logical, other

Q6x What other paradigm is being taught?

Q7 Do you encourage students in this first programming course to use environments and/or tools beyond simple text editors and command line compilers? Yes / No. If No is chosen, skip to Q8

Q7a Which environment or tool do you use? Please select all that apply:

AdaCore-GPS, Alice, App Inventor, Bloodshed Dev C++, BlueJ, Browser and extensions, Eclipse, Homegrown/Custom IDE, Greenfoot, Idle, JCreator, Jeroo, JES, Jupyter Notebooks or JupyterLab, KTechLab, Matlab, Mindstorms NXT or EV3, MS Visual Studio, MySQL Workbench, Netbeans, PellesC, Processing, Quincy, Spyder/Rodeo, Wing101, XCode, some other environment.

Q7x Which other environment/tool do you use?

[Begin repeated block, for each environment chosen]

Q7c <Environment> is used:

- a) For an initial part of the first programming course
- b) Throughout the first programming course

c) After another environment/language in the course

Q7d Is <Environment> used in any other courses in the degree? Yes/No

Q7e This question asks about why <Environment> is used in your course, and asks you to rate the importance of each reason. If a reason is not applicable, please choose N/A. Otherwise how important was each reason? N/A, slightly important, important, very important.

Associated support material, Availability/Cost to students, Cross-platform, Ease of installation, Graphical User Interface, Open source, OS/Machine limitations of department, packaged with the language, pedagogical benefits, plugins available, relevant to industry, student motivation, suitable for online delivery, supports OO paradigm, uncomplicated/ease of use, visual cues/debugger, other.

Q7f How difficult do YOU find <Environment> to use?
extremely easy, somewhat easy, neither easy nor difficult, somewhat difficult, extremely difficult.

Q7g On average, how difficult do you believe **THE STUDENTS** find <environment> to use?
extremely easy, somewhat easy, neither easy nor difficult, somewhat difficult, extremely difficult.

[END OF REPEATED BLOCK]

Q8 How many years have you been involved in the teaching of introductory programming?
Under 2 years, 2-5 years, over 5 years – 10 years, over 10 years – 20 years, over 20 years – 30 years, over 30 years.

Q9 Do you currently offer online delivery of your course?
(i.e. do you have options for your course where students are not required to attend any regular lectures, workshops, labs or tutorials, but can complete their study online?) Yes / No

Q9a (Displayed if Yes is chosen above)
Did you offer online delivery of your course prior to the Covid-19 pandemic? Yes/No.

Q9b Do you intend to keep offering online delivery of your course post-pandemic?
Yes / Maybe / No

Q10 Do you consider the possibility that when doing assignments, students or groups of students may be receiving unauthorised assistance - for example, from other students in the class, from people outside the class, or via the internet? Yes / No. If no, go to Q11.

Q10a How concerned are you at the thought that students or groups of students might be receiving unauthorised assistance on assignments?
Not concerned, somewhat concerned, very concerned

Q10b What steps do you take to try to determine whether students have received unauthorised assistance on assignments? (choose as many as apply)
none, notice unexpected elements in the code, notice unlikely similarities between different programs, use a software similarity detection system, interview some

students/groups selected at random, interview some students/groups when suspicions are aroused, interview all students/groups, require students/groups to give presentations explaining their work, other.

Q10c What other steps do you take?

Q10d What action do you take if you determine that students/groups have received unauthorised assistance, and do you feel well supported by your institution in taking these actions? [Open text response]

Q11 Which of the following resources do you provide for your students? Choose all that apply:

Assignment hints, 'Cheat sheets' (student produced notes) in exams, discussion boards/forums, glossaries of keywords, lecture slides or notes – provided by textbook publisher, lecture slides or notes – provided by lecturer, mailing list/discord community or similar, open book examinations, online examinations, online tutorials, recorded lectures, self-assessment questions, textbook is specified, topic summaries, worked examples of programming problems/solutions, other resources.

Q11x What other resources do you provide?

[if online exams are chosen above in Q11, show Q11a]

Q11a Did you offer online examinations prior to the Covid-19 pandemic? Yes / no

Q12 What do you consider to be the three most important aims of an introductory programming course? Use a few words for each.

Q12a Aim 1:

Q12b Aim 2:

Q12c Aim 3:

[for each of these aims]

Q12d How helpful is your current programming language/s in meeting these aims? Extremely helpful, very helpful, moderately helpful, slightly helpful, not helpful at all.

Q13 How do you think the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted on the teaching of introductory programming? [open text answer]

Q14 If there are any other comments you would like to offer about the teaching of introductory programming, please use the space below.

Q15 If you know of any other introductory programming courses at your university, it would be appreciated if you could pass the invitation to participate in this survey to the instructors who run them. It would also be appreciated if you would pass this invitation to your network of computing educators.

Q16 If you would like a summary of the results of this study, please click YES - you will be taken to a separate survey where you will be able to enter your email address. In this way, your responses to the survey cannot be associated with your email address. Yes / No